

DL5.3 – Association of third countries with similar plant health problems as the EU

DL5.4 – Association of third countries who are the source of quarantine pests of concern to the EU

EUPHRESCO-II

**DEEPENED AND ENLARGED COOPERATION BETWEEN PHYTOSANITARY
(STATUTORY PLANT HEALTH) RESEARCH PROGRAMMES**

COORDINATION ACTION (ERA-NET)

Grant No: 266505

DL5.3 – Association of third countries with similar plant health problems as the EU

The activities relating to this Deliverable are presented below and the Concept for Merging Plan is presented in **Annex 1** (included as a document in the EUPHRESCO Tool Box):

- International Cooperation Department in Warszawa, Poland represented by Mrs Olesia Witowska has in October 2011 delivered an official request to join EUPHRESCO-2; the Polish candidate partners were invited to attend the first annual meeting in February 2012. Unfortunately, they were not able to join in the end, though remaining in contact with the Project. Polish membership will be explored further in the long-term Network via EPPO.
- WP Leader Steen Lykke Nielsen invited Dr Yuval Eshdat, The Chief Scientist, Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development of Israel to join EUPHRESCO-2, but until now without success.
- WP- leader Steen Lykke Nielsen has since June 2012 contacted an Israeli scientist (V. Soroker), who has expressed high interest in collaboration with EUPHRESCO to contact an Israeli funder for further progress. No response has yet been obtained.
- Furthermore B. Stephenson in the Science Policy team in the Ministry of Agriculture & Forestry of New Zealand has been invited to explore EUPHRESCO and the possibility to be associated partner. No response has yet been obtained.
- A merging plan for associating 3rd countries has been developed and adopted by the EUPHRESCO's General Assembly at the First Annual Project Meeting 14–15 February 2012 in Rome and by the PMG at the following PMG-meeting 16 February 2012 in Rome. The merging plan was adopted (for EUPHRESCO-2) and included in the Toolbook on the EUPHRESCO web-site as follows:
 - 3rd countries will be offered status as observers
 - 3rd country observers will have to fill in a Letter of intent
 - 3rd country observers will have full access to topic proposal lists but only access to results from the projects they participate in
 - 3rd country observers are expected to raise funding for participation in at least one round of research topic market place
 - 3rd country observers are expected to respond and deliver material to requests and questionnaires from the different WPs

DL5.4 – Association of third countries who are the source of quarantine pests of concern to the EU

The activities relating to this Deliverable are presented below and the Concept for Affiliating 3rd Countries is presented in **Annex 2** (included as a document in the EUPHRESCO Tool Box) and the outputs from the ‘Mediterranean’ Workshop in **Annex 3**:

- Steen Lykke Nielsen and several other EUPHRESCO-2 partners active in WP5 participated in the EFSA Scientific Colloquium XIV on Emerging Risks in Plant Health 9–10 June 2011 in Parma, Italy and in an EFSA and Finnish Food Safety Authority seminar on Risk Assessment in Plant Health 1-3 October 2012 in Helsinki, Finland. The themes of the Colloquium and seminar is very relevant for the WP5 topics: regionalisation and import of plant health problems from third world countries.
- Steen Lykke Nielsen met with Head of Business Development Europe Janny Vos and Business Development Director Philip Abrahams from CABI (who are an Observer in EUPHRESCO-2) at Aarhus University the 29 June 2011 to discuss activities in EUPHRESCO-2’s WP5 with focus on activities in third world countries to prevent import of plant health problems.
- The main challenge to develop a concept associating 3rd countries “*which are the source of quarantine pests of concern to the EU*”, is that EUPHRESCO does not hold a specific grant for that purpose. Therefore the concept must build on the principle to involve 3rd countries in the research topic initiation rounds, so the participation of 3rd country partners can be financed by the EUPHRESCO initiated transnational projects. In fact, in the 2nd topic round, a project on plant health risks of wood chips imported from 3rd countries was proposed, which demands participation of an exporting firm or a plant inspection service authority from a 3rd country; the resulting project achieved this. If the concept is widened also to include EUPHRESCO partners housing a quarantine pest under eradication and not yet spread to other EU members, another topic was proposed involving activities with the pine wood nematode in Portugal by other EUPHRESCO partners. The same is the matter with a running EUPHRESCO project on Asian long horned beetle, where some of the activities are carried out in an infested district Lombardy in Italy and a project on potato flea beetle with activities in an infected district in Portugal. The project has also included a study visit to an infested district in the USA, making contact with the US authorities and a research institute, even though those are not officially associated the project. A concept for affiliating project partners from 3rd countries to EUPHRESCO-2 initiated research projects has been worked out and included in the Toolbook on the EUPHRESCO web-site (**Annex 2**).

At the First Annual Project Meeting 14–15 February 2012 in Rome the General Assembly decided to ask WP5 to arrange a workshop with representative from a North African NPPO (the Near East Plant Protection Organization - NEPPO) and other North African countries to be invited to participate in the next Annual Project Meeting to discuss plant health problems related to import of plant products from that region and possibilities of

association to future EUPHRESKO initiated projects. This resulted in a workshop entitled “Exploring plant health problems of concern with special emphasis on Mediterranean partners of EPPO and EUPHRESKO” held 13 March 2013 in Portugal with participation of representatives from NEPPO and Algeria (**Annex 3**).

A comparison of the Partner (light grey) and Observer (dark grey) coverage by country in the previous EUPHRESKO-I (left) and in EUPHRESKO-II (right)

Annex 1 – Concept for a Merging Plan

A concept for merging third countries with the EUPHRESKO network

Concept:

- 3rd country observers will have to fill in a Letter of Intent.
- 3rd country observers will have full access to topic proposal lists from the electronic topic market place, but only access to results from the projects they participate in and NOT from all projects.
- 3rd country observers are expected to raise funding for participation in at least one round of research topic market place. Funding could be in form of manpower, laboratory capacity and not necessarily cash to be delivered to a common pool.
- 3rd country observers are expected to respond and deliver material to requests and questionnaires from EUPHRESKO.

The concept also covers participants in specific EUPHRESKO initiated projects, who are not EUPHRESKO-2 members or observers.

The concept will have to be modified for the long term sustainable EUPHRESKO network, because the observer category probably will disappear.

The concept was adopted for EUPHRESKO-2 at the Annual meeting in Lisbon 2013.

Annex 2 – A Concept for Affiliating Project Partners from 3rd Countries

A concept for affiliating project partners from third countries to EUPHRESKO-2 initiated research projects

Concept:

- 3rd country project partners could be research providers, plant trading and production partners.
- 3rd country project partners will have to fill in a Letter of Commitment.
- 3rd country project partners will only have access to results from the projects they participate in and NOT from all EUPHRESKO initiated projects.

Initiating the association of 3rd countries:

- The funders of EUPHRESKO-2 research projects might in the topic call text encouraged the applicants to include the participation of a firm or research partner from a 3rd country¹). (This should not be a compulsory demand, but only a request).
- EUPHRESKO partners arranging or participating in workshops/conferences with 3rd countries²).

Funding:

- EUPHRESKO-2 does not have a separate grant to finance transnational research activities with partners in 3rd countries.
- Project partners from 3rd countries might be included in the funds of transnational funded EUPHRESKO research projects, meaning that it is the participating EUPHRESKO partners who fund the 3rd country partners' activities in the project. (This might raise some legal problems for some EUPHRESKO partners).
- 3rd country project partners might participate under their own resources in cases they have their own specific interest.

Topic substances phytosanitary ideas:

Experiments with selected quarantine pests in their natural environments and host plants.

Establishment of sentinel plantings (acting as bait plants to attract new pests or planting selected plant species in a region known to harbor certain pathogens and in this manner determine the susceptibility of the different plant species).

Focus on a specific plant production in a specific enterprise: analysis of the problem, compilation of an activity plan, execution of the plan etc.

Capacity building in the 3rd country to improve inspection of plant production enterprises before export to Europe as for example:

Improving diagnostic expertise (could involve 3rd country project partners as ring test partners in diagnostic projects)

Improving expertise in detection.

Improving preventive measures to be directed (enjoined) the enterprises.

The concept was adopted for EUPHRESKO-2 at the Annual meeting in Lisbon March 2013.

- 1) This approach was included in the call text of the EUPHRESCO-2 Woodchip-project launched May 2013.
- 2) This approach was used by EUPHRESCO-2 arranging a workshop titled “Exploring plant health problems of concern with special emphasis on Mediterranean partners of EPPO and EUPHRESCO” 13th March 2013 in Portugal with presentations of representatives from NEPPO (the Near East Plant Protection Organization), EUPHRESCO-2 and specific countries by Algeria and Portugal.

Annex 3 – Report on workshop entitled “*Exploring plant health problems of concern with special emphasis on Mediterranean partners of EPPO and EUPHRESKO*”

EUPHRESCO Workshop - Exploring plant health problems of concern with special emphasis on Mediterranean partners of EPPO and EUPHRESCO.
Monte Estoril, Portugal 13 March 2013

Report of the workshop by Sylvia Blümel & Steen Lykke Nielsen

Participants.

All EUPHRESCO-2 partners and observers were invited to the workshop.

The following persons participated:

Andrade, Eugénia	Instituto Nacional de Investigação Agrária e Veterinária (INIAV), PT
Anthoine, Geraldine	Laboratoire de la santé des végétaux, ANSES, FR
Benddine, Fatiha	Protection des Végétaux et des Contrôles Techniques – Ministère de l’Agriculture et du Développement Rural, DZ
Blümel, Sylvia	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES), AT
Burcak, Alev	Ministry Food, Agriculture & Livestock, TR
Canada, Nuno	Instituto Nacional de Investigação Agrária e Veterinária (INIA), PT
Candresse, Thierry	INRA, FR
Carvalho, Ana Paula	Plant Health Department from Direção-Geral de Agricultura e Veterinária, PT
Chouibani, Mekki	Near East Plant Protection Organization (NEPPO), MA
Cruz, Leonor	Instituto Nacional de Recursos Biológicos, I.P. (INIA), PT
Egartner, Alois	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES), AT
Inman, Alan	Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (Defra), UK
Jerabek, Ladislav	Ministry of Agriculture, CZ
Kaare, Kylli	Ministry Agriculture, Research & Development, EE
Karadjova, Olia	Agricultural Academy, BG
Kenyon, David	Science and Advice for Scottish Agriculture (SASA), UK
Lopes, Amélia	Instituto Nacional de Investigação Agrária e Veterinária (INIAV), PT
Maes, Martine	Instituut voor Landbouw- en Visserijonderzoek (ILVO), BE
Nielsen, Steen Lykke	Aarhus University (AU), DK
Nouwen, Ria	Federale Overheidstdienst Volkgesondheist, BE
Olivier, Thibaut	Life Sciences Department, BE
Peña, Anabel de la	Instituto Nacional de Innovacion Agraria, ES
Regouin, Eric	Ministry Economic affairs, Agriculture & Innovation, NL

São Simão, Carlos Plant Health Department from Direção-Geral de Agricultura e Veterinária, PT

Schachermayr, Gabr. Swiss Federal Plant Protection Service (SPPS), CH

Schans, Jan Wageningen UR, NL

Steel, Elspeth Defra, Plant Health Policy Programme, UK

Steinmüller, Silke Julius Kühn-Institut, D

Vloutoglou, Irene Benaki Phytopathological Institute, GR

Annexes

The following annexes were mailed to the participants as background material for the workshop:
Programme

Annex 0. Introduction to background material

Annex 1. Overview of harmful organisms listed in EPPO's Alert List (last updated 2013-01)

Annex 2. Overview of harmful organisms present in the Mediterranean region and listed in EPPO's Alert List

Annex 3a. List of EU's interceptions 2011

Annex 3b. List of EU's interceptions January 2013

Annex 4. List of EU's emergency measures on Q-pests March 2013

Annex 5. Conclusions from the EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant

health problems in the region of Balkan and Eastern Europe in Sofia 28th – 29th February 2012

Aims and conclusions of the workshop

- Aim 1. To **explore plant health problems of concern** with special emphasis on Mediterranean partners of EPPO, NEPPO and EUPHRESCO

Conclusion:

The presentations from the Northern and Southern Mediterranean regions showed many phytosanitary pests of mutual interest for EPPO, NEPPO and EUPHRESCO.

- Specifically addressed were:

-the further development of rapid screening tests which can be used at border inspection for detection and identification of phytosanitary pests.

-as examples of important pests were mentioned and discussed citrus greening (Huanglongbin) and fruitflies e.g. *Anastrepha* species from South America and *Bactrocera zonata*.

- Aim 2. To explore **potential possibilities of co-operation** between EPPO, NEPPO and EUPHRESCO partners to solve plant health problems of concern.

Conclusion:

- offer the opportunity for non-EUPHRESCO members to participate in the validation of detection and diagnostic methods of phytosanitary pests.
- EUPHRESCO project leaders should be encouraged to inform about parts of a project, which allows participation of additional interested partners (who are formally not project partners) as for example validation test.
- increase in transfer of knowledge about existing rapid detection and identification methods.
- offer the opportunity to non-EUPHRESCO members to participate as observer at meetings of ongoing EUPHRESCO projects.
- identify relevant funders and programme managers in NEPPO/EPPO countries.
- Aim 3. To **explore interest** among EPPO, NEPPO members **to benefit from EUPHRESCO's activities**

Conclusion:

- Yes, there was among the workshop participants great interest.

Abstract of the presentations

Introduction to the workshop by Sylvia Blümel.

In the presentation was introduced the aims of the workshop:

- to explore plant health problems of concern with special emphasis on Mediterranean partners of EPPO, NEPPO and EUPHRESCO
- to explore potential possibilities of co-operation between EPPO, NEPPO and EUPHRESCO partners to solve plant health problems of concern
- to explore interest among EPPO, NEPPO members to benefit from EUPHRESCO's activities

Short introduction to EUPHRESCO and the Work Package about co-operation with 3rd countries.

Overview of the transnational research projects initiated by EUPHRESCO by Sylvia Blümel.

Sylvia Blümel gave a short introduction to EUPHRESCO-1 and -2 with especial emphasis on work package 5, under which the workshop is arranged. Topics mentioned were among other things benefits and added values for the members and observers, and the many transnational phytosanitary projects initiated by EUPHRESCO.

Short introduction to background information from EPPO's Alert List, EU interceptions and emergency measures by Steen Lykke Nielsen.

The background information in form of the annexes was shortly introduced.

Important phytosanitary pests of concern and threats in the Near East region and in particular problems with pests originating from EU member states. Visions on possible future co-operation between NEPPO and EUPHRESCO by Mekki Chouibani.

Mekki Chouibani gave a short introduction to NEPPO (the Near East Plant Protection Organization) with members from Algeria, Egypt, Jordan, Libya, Malta, Morocco, Pakistan, Sudan, Syria, Tunisia. Some of these countries are also members of EPPO. The aims of NEPPO are

- To promote international cooperation and strengthen capacities.
- Controlling pests in an appropriate manner
- Preventing the spread and introduction of pests
- Facilitate safe regional and international trade

Some pests of important phytosanitary concern were: Red Palm Weevil: *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus*, *Paysandisia archon*, pine wood nematode: *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus*, Plum Pox Virus, fireblight: *Erwinia amylovora*, potato brown rot: *Ralstonia solanacearum*, potato ringrot: *Clavibacter michiganense* spp *sepedonicus*, *Phytophthora ramorum*, *Drosophila suzuki*, Citrus Tristeza virus(CTV) and CTV vector *Toxoptera citricida*.

Vision of possible future co-operation between NEPPO and EUPHRESCO comprised the following dots:

- NEPPO: young Regional plant protection organization (RPPO).
- Lack of research in plant protection within the Near East because of limited resources.
- Overlaps in research topics within the country and the region.
- EUPHRESCO: good model to better coordinate research and optimize use of the limited resources.
- EPPO has great experience in EUPHRESCO programs.
- Experience of countries, members of EPPO and NEPPO, in the process will facilitate to extend it to other Near East countries.
- EPPO, will host EUPHRESCO co-ordination, experience will help NEPPO in implementing this model.
- NPPO are involved with RPPO.
- Research in plant protection issues is done by many national institutions; the challenge is to identify a coordinator (NPPO) and how to deal with financial contribution.
- Importance of Citrus within the Mediterranean area.
- Develop methods for detection and identification of this disease and its vectors.
- Develop a survey approach.
- Develop a management system for quick response in case of introduction.
- Implement a survey network on greening disease.

Exploring plant health problems of concern with special emphasis on Mediterranean partners of EPPO and EUPHRESCO by Fatiha Benddine.

Fatiha Benddine gave a short introduction to the sector of agriculture in the People's Democratic Republic of Algeria. Examples of phytosanitary problems in main crops were in cereals: rust yellow, Septoria and Helminthosporia; in tomato: leaf-miners, mites, whiteflies and downy mildiou; in potato: downy mildew and moth; in citrus: leaf miners and fruit flies; in date palms: mites and moth date; in olive: olive fruit fly; in fruit cultures: fire blight in pears and *Cacopsylla*. It was stressed that the following quarantine pests are absent in Algeria: red palm weevil, *Ralstonia solanacearum* and *Clavibacter michiganense* spp *sepedonicus*. Fatiha Benddine gave some examples of successfully IPM experiences realized and based on biological control comprising control of *Aleurothrixus floccosus* with *Cales noacki*, *Icerya purchasi* with *Novius cardinalis*,

Bemisia tabaci with *Encarsia formosa* and use of trapping to control *Tuta absoluta*. Examples of interceptions at the control of import from EU countries on borders comprised *Helminthosporium solani*, *Streptomyces scabies* and *Erwinia carotovora* in potato; *Aonidiella aurantii* in citrus; *Pseudomonas savastanoi* in olive plants; Citrus Tristeza virus in ornamental plant.

Important phytosanitary pests of concern and threats in Portugal and in particular problems with pests originating from the Near East region by Paula Cruz de Carvalho. Paula Cruz de Carvalho gave a short introduction to the General Directorate for Food and Veterinary and the plant health authority in Portugal. The following important phytosanitary pests of concern and threats in Portugal were selected for deepening: Grapevine flavescence doreé MLO, *Erwinia amylovora*, *Drosophila suzukii* and the pine wood nematode. Specific threats from the Near East mentioned were Tomato apical stunt pospiviroid, *Thaumatotibia leucotreta* (false codling moth) and *Bactrocera invadens* (a fruit fly).

Appendixes

Programme

EUPHRESCO Workshop - Exploring plant health problems of concern with special emphasis on Mediterranean partners of EPPO and EUPHRESCO

Monte Estoril, Portugal 13 March 2013

- 08.30** **Registration**
- 09.00** **Welcome by Nuno Canada** (Management Board of Instituto Nacional de Investigação Agrária e Veterinária, Portugal)
- 09.10** **Introduction to the workshop by Sylvia Blümel** (Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES))
- 09.20** **Short introduction to EUPHRESCO and the Work Package about co-operation with 3rd countries. Overview of the transnational research projects initiated by EUPHRESCO by Sylvia Blümel** (AGES)
- 09.50** **Short introduction to background information from EPPO's Alert List, EU interceptions and emergency measures by Steen Lykke Nielsen** (Aarhus University)
- 10.10** **Important phytosanitary pests of concern and threats in the Near East region and in particular problems with pests originating from EU member states. Visions on possible future co-operation between NEPPO and EUPHRESCO by Mekki Chouibani** (Near East Plant Protection Organization, Morocco)
- 10.40** **Tea/Coffee**
- 11.10** **Important phytosanitary pests of concern and threats in Algeria and in particular problems with pests originating from EU member states. Interests in future co-operation with EUPHRESCO by Fatiha Benddine** (Protection des Végétaux et des Contrôles Techniques – Ministère de l'Agriculture et du Développement Rural, Alger)
- 11.40** **Important phytosanitary pests of concern and threats in Portugal and in particular problems with pests originating from the Near East region by Ana Paula Carvalho** (Plant Health Department from Direção-Geral de Agricultura e Veterinária, Portugal)
- 12.10** **Discussions and conclusions**
- 12.45** **Summary of conclusions by Sylvia Blümel & Steen Lykke Nielsen**
- 12.55** **Closing the workshop by Sylvia Blümel**
- 13.00** **Lunch**
- 15.00-17.00** **Start of the EUPHRESCO Yearly Assembly Meeting**

Annex 0

Introduction to Annexes.

Annex 1. Overview of harmful organisms listed in EPPO's Alert List (last updated 2013-01). This annex gives an overview of actual plant health treats origin from all over the world sorted on crop sectors and crops.

Annex 2. Overview of harmful organisms present in the Mediterranean region and listed in EPPO's Alert List. As Annex 1, but restricted to the Mediterranean region.

Annex 3a. List of EU's interceptions 2011. The list states import of quarantine pests into the European Union, so in nature of the case, the list only comprises non-European Union member states. The list only comprises countries from North Africa and the Near East. The list in full can be downloaded from http://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/europhyt/interceptions_en.htm . The list gives an impression of the q-pest problems notified by EU.

Annex 3b. List of EU's interceptions January 2013. This is the most actual list published covering January month 2013.

Annex 4. List of EU's emergency measures on Q-pests March 2013. The list gives information on which q-pest the EU Commission is most alert on at the moment.

Annex 5. Conclusions from the EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of Balkan and Eastern Europe in Sofia 28th – 29th February 2012. Some of the participants in the Balkan-Eastern European workshop are Mediterranean countries (Greece, Turkey, Cyprus). Therefore it has some informative interest to be informed about which specific plant health pests were found most important, during the workshop.

Annex 1

Overview of harmful organisms listed in EPPO's Alert List (last updated 2013-01).

Crop sector	Crops	Organism group	Species	Distribution
Tomato	Tomato			
1. Agriculture, glasshouse	Tomato	Virus etc.	<i>Tomato apical stunt pospiviroid</i>	Israel, Côte d'Ivoire, Senegal, Tunisia, Indonesia
2. Agriculture, glasshouse	Tomato	Virus etc.	Tomato torrado virus	Panama, Australia
3. Glasshouse, agriculture	Tomato, aubergine, Capsicum	Insect (Lepidoptora)	<i>Neoleucinodes elegantalis</i>	South and Central America, Caribbean, Mexico
Potato	Potato			
4. Agriculture, glasshouse, fruit	Cereals, vegetables, sunflower, maize, potato	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne ethiopica</i>	Ethiopia, Kenya, Mozambique, South Africa, Tanzania, Zimbabwe, Brazil, Chile
Maize	Maize			
5. Agriculture, fruit	Citrus, stone fruit, cotton, maize	Insect	<i>Thaumatotibia leucotreta</i>	Widespread Africa, Israel
6. Agriculture, glasshouse, fruit	Cereals, vegetables, sunflower, maize, potato	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne ethiopica</i>	Ethiopia, Kenya, Mozambique, South Africa, Tanzania, Zimbabwe, Brazil, Chile
7. Fruit, citrus fruit, plants for planting, agriculture	Citrus, pome, stonefruit, maize, soybean, ornamental trees & shrubs etc.	Insect	<i>Halyomorpha halys</i>	China, Korea, Japan, Taiwan, USA
8. Agriculture	Maize (<i>Zea mays</i>) and other cereals (<i>Triticum</i> , <i>Hordeum</i>)	Nematode	<i>Hederodera zae</i>	India, Nepal, Pakistan, Thailand, Egypt, USA
9. Agriculture	Maize (<i>Zea mays</i>)	Nematode	<i>Punctodera chalcoensis</i>	Mexico

10. Agriculture	Maize (<i>Zea mays</i>)	Phytoplasma	Maize redness (stolbur phytoplasma)	Europe: Bulgaria, Croatia, Hungary, Italy, Romania and Serbia.
Other agriculture crops	Other agriculture crops			
11. Agriculture	Sunflower	Insect	<i>Strauzia longipennis</i>	North America
12. Agriculture, fruit	Citrus, stone fruit, cotton, maize	Insect	<i>Thaumatotibia leucotreta</i>	Widespread Africa, Israel
13. Agriculture, glasshouse, fruit	Cereals, vegetables, sunflower, maize, potato	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne ethiopica</i>	Ethiopia, Kenya, Mozambique, South Africa, Tanzania, Zimbabwe, Brazil, Chile
14. Agriculture, glasshouse	Lettuce	Fungi	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> f.sp. <i>lactucae</i>	Iran, Japan, Korea, Taiwan, USA
15. Agriculture	Sugar beet	Bacteria Insect vector	Syndrome des basses richesses, γ -proteobacterium 'Candidatus Arsenophonus phytopathogenicus' <i>Pentastiridius leporinus</i>	France, Germany, Hungary Nearly all EPPO countries. Africa: Algeria, Tunisia
Glasshouse	Glasshouse			
Fruit	Fruit			
16. Citrus fruit, agriculture	Citrus, melon	Bacteria	<i>Acidovorax citrulli</i>	China, Japan, Taiwan, Thailand, USA, Brazil, Costa Rica, Australia
17. Fruit	Peach, apricot, plum, cherry	Insect	<i>Aromia bungii</i> , Redneck longhorned beetle	China, Korea, Mongolia, Taiwan, Vietnam
18. Fruit, citrus fruit, plants for planting,	Citrus, pome, stonefruit, maize, soybean,	Insect	<i>Halyomorpha halys</i>	China, Korea, Japan, Taiwan, USA

agriculture	ornamental trees & shrubs etc.			
19. Forestry, fruit, plants for planting	Citrus, many trees, stonefruit a.o. fruits	Insect	<i>Oemona hirta</i> , lemon tree borer	N.Z.
Plants for planting	Plants for planting			
20. Plants for planting	Horse chestnut	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas syringae</i> pv. <i>aesculi</i>	India
21. Forestry, plants for planting	Ash	Fungi	<i>Chalara fraxinea</i>	Widespread in Europa
22. Forestry, plants for planting	Beech, rhododendron	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora kernoviae</i>	N.Z.
23. Plants for planting, forestry	Rhododendron, Camellia, Viburnum, oak	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>	USA
24. Fruit, citrus fruit, plants for planting, agriculture	Citrus, pome, stonefruit, maize, soybean, ornamental trees & shrubs etc.	Insect	<i>Halyomorpha halys</i>	China, Korea, Japan, Taiwan, USA
25. Forestry, fruit, plants for planting	Citrus, many trees, stonefruit a.o. fruits	Insect	<i>Oemona hirta</i>	N.Z.
26. Plants for planting	Daylilies (<i>Hemerocallis</i>)	Insect (Diptera)	<i>Ophiomyia kwansonis</i>	Japan, Taiwan, USA
Forestry	Forestry			
27. Forestry	<i>Eucalyptus</i>	Insect	<i>Chrysophtharta bimaculata</i> , Tasmanian eucalyptus leaf beetle	N.Z.
28. Forestry	Oak species	Insect	<i>Enaphalodes rufulus</i> , red oak borer	North America
29. Forestry	Pine	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora pinifolia</i>	Chile
30. Forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Xylosandrus crassiusculus</i> , Asian ambrosia beetle	Widespread Asia, Africa, USA, Costa Rica, Panama, New Caledonia, Palau, Papua New Guinea, Samoa
31. Forestry, plants for planting	Ash	Fungi	<i>Chalara fraxinea</i>	Widespread in Europa
32. Forestry, plants for planting	Beech, rhododendron	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora kernoviae</i>	N.Z.

33. Plants for planting, forestry	Rhododendron, Camellia, Viburnum, oak	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>	USA
34. Forestry, fruit, plants for planting	Citrus, many trees, stonefruit a.o. fruits	Insect	<i>Oeomona hirta</i>	N.Z.
35. Forestry	Ulmus sp.	Insect	<i>Aproceros leucopoda</i> , Zigzag elm sawfly	China, Japan, Russia
36. Forestry	Abies sp.	Insect	<i>Polygraphus proximus</i>	China, Japan, Korea, Russia
37. Forestry	Eucalyptus trees	Insect (Hemiptera)	<i>Thaumastocoris peregrinus</i>	S. America, Australia, NZ, S. & E. Africa

Annex 2

Overview of harmful organisms present in the Mediterranean region and listed in EPPO's Alert List (last updated 2013-01).

Crop sector	Crops	Organism group	Species	Distribution
Tomato	Tomato			
38. Agriculture, glasshouse	Tomato	Virus etc.	<i>Tomato apical stunt pospiviroid</i>	Israel, Côte d'Ivoire, Senegal, Tunisia, Indonesia
Potato	Potato			
Maize	Maize			
39. Agriculture, fruit	Citrus, stone fruit, cotton, maize	Insect	<i>Thaumatotibia leucotreta</i>	Widespread Africa, Israel
40. Agriculture	Maize (<i>Zea mays</i>)	Phytoplasma	Maize redness (stolbur phytoplasma)	Europe: Bulgaria, Croatia, Hungary, Italy, Romania and Serbia.
41. Agriculture	Maize (<i>Zea mays</i>) and other cereals (<i>Triticum</i> , <i>Hordeum</i>)	Nematode	<i>Heterodera zeae</i>	India, Nepal, Pakistan, Thailand, Egypt, USA
Other agriculture crops	Other agriculture crops			
42. Agriculture, fruit	Citrus, stone fruit, cotton, maize	Insect	<i>Thaumatotibia leucotreta</i>	Widespread Africa, Israel
43. Agriculture	Sugar beet	Bacteria Insect vector	Syndrome des basses richesses, γ -proteobacterium 'Candidatus <i>Arsenophonus phytopathogenicus</i> ' <i>Pentastiridius leporinus</i>	France, Germany, Hungary Nearly all EPPO countries. N.Africa: Algeria, Tunisia
Glasshouse	Glasshouse			
Fruit	Fruit			
Plants for planting	Plants for planting			
44. Forestry, plants	Ash	Fungi	<i>Chalara fraxinea</i>	Widespread in

for planting				Europa
Forestry	Forestry			
45. Forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Xylosandrus crassiusculus</i> , Asian ambrosia beetle	Widespread Asia, Africa, USA, Costa Rica, Panama, New Caledonia, Palau, Papua New Guinea, Samoa
46. Forestry, plants for planting	Ash	Fungi	<i>Chalara fraxinea</i>	Widespread in Europa

Annex 3a

List of EU's interceptions 2011.

Interceptions of harmful organisms in commodities imported into the EU or Switzerland

Notified during: 2011

Country of Export	Commodity	Plant Species	Harmful Organism	No. of Interceptions
EGYPT	OTHER LIVING PLANTS : CUT FLOWERS AND BRANCHES WITH FOLIAGE	CHRYSANTHEMUM SP.	LIRIOMYZA TRIFOLII	1
		OTHER LIVING PLANTS : FRUIT & VEGETABLES	ANNONA SP.	BACTROCERA SP.
	CERATITIS SP.			1
	MANGIFERA INDICA		TEPHRITIDAE (NON-EUROPEAN)	1
	OCIMUM BASILICUM		LIRIOMYZA SP	1
	PSIDIUM GUAJAVA	CERATITIS CAPITATA	1	

EGYPT	OTHER LIVING PLANTS : FRUIT & VEGETABLES	PSIDIUM GUAJAVA	CERATITIS SP.	2
			TEPHRITIDAE (NON-EUROPEAN)	1
		PSIDIUM SP.	TEPHRITIDAE (NON-EUROPEAN)	2
EGYPT			<i>Sum:</i>	12

Country of Export	Commodity	Plant Species	Harmful Organism	No. of Interceptions
ISRAEL	INTENDED FOR PLANTING : CUTTINGS	AJUGA SP.	BEMISIA TABACI	1
		CAPSICUM ANNUUM	BEMISIA TABACI	1
		DIANTHUS SP.	LIRIOMYZA HUIDOBRENSIS	1
		ERYSIMUM SP.	ALEYRODIDAE	1
			BEMISIA TABACI	5
		GYPSOPHILA SP.	LIRIOMYZA HUIDOBRENSIS	1
		IMPATIENS SP	LIRIOMYZA HUIDOBRENSIS	1
		LAVATERA SP.	BEMISIA TABACI	1
		LEPIDIUM SP.	LIRIOMYZA HUIDOBRENSIS	1
		LIPPIA SP.	BEMISIA TABACI	1
MANDEVILLA SP	BEMISIA SP.	1		

ISRAEL	INTENDED FOR PLANTING : CUTTINGS	MANDEVILLA SP	BEMISIA TABACI	1
		OSTEOSPERMUM SP.	LIRIOMYZA HUIDOBRENSIS	1
		PENTAGLOTTIS SP.	LIRIOMYZA HUIDOBRENSIS	1
		SALVIA OFFICINALIS	BEMISIA TABACI	5
		VERBENA SP.	BEMISIA TABACI	1
			LIRIOMYZA HUIDOBRENSIS	1
	INTENDED FOR PLANTING : NOT YET PLANTED	DIPLADENIA SP.	BEMISIA TABACI	1
		LAVATERA SP.	BEMISIA TABACI	1
		LIPPIA SP.	BEMISIA TABACI	2
	OTHER LIVING PLANTS : CUT FLOWERS AND BRANCHES WITH FOLIAGE	CAPSELLA BURSA-PASTORIS	BEMISIA SP.	2
		DIANTHUS BARBATUS	LIRIOMYZA TRIFOLII	1
		GYPSOPHILA SP.	LIRIOMYZA SP	6
			LIRIOMYZA TRIFOLII	4
		LISIANTHUS SP.	BEMISIA TABACI	1
MANDEVILLA SP		BEMISIA TABACI	1	

ISRAEL	OTHER LIVING PLANTS : CUT FLOWERS AND BRANCHES WITH FOLIAGE	OCIMUM BASILICUM	BEMISIA TABACI	1
		SOLIDAGO SP.	BEMISIA TABACI	7
			LIRIOMYZA TRIFOLII	2
		TRACHELIUM	BEMISIA TABACI	1
		TRACHELIUM SP.	BEMISIA TABACI	2
	OTHER LIVING PLANTS : FRUIT & VEGETABLES	DIOSPYROS SP.	TEPHRITIDAE (NON-EUROPEAN)	1
		OCIMUM BASILICUM	BEMISIA TABACI	55
			LIRIOMYZA	3
			LIRIOMYZA SATIVAE	12
			LIRIOMYZA SP	6
			LIRIOMYZA TRIFOLII	1
			SPODOPTERA LITTORALIS	1
		OCIMUM SP.	BEMISIA TABACI	4
	LIRIOMYZA SP		1	
SALVIA SP.	BEMISIA TABACI	1		

ISRAEL	OTHER LIVING PLANTS : FRUIT & VEGETABLES	SOLIDAGO SP.	BEMISIA TABACI	1
	OTHER LIVING PLANTS : LEAVES	OCIMUM BASILICUM	THRIPIDAE	1
		ORIGANUM VULGARE	BEMISIA SP.	1
		SATUREJA SP.	BEMISIA SP.	1
			LIRIOMYZA SP	1
	OTHER LIVING PLANTS : ! OTHERS	ORCHIDACEAE	FRANKLINIELLA OCCIDENTALIS	1
		ORIGANUM VULGARE	BEMISIA TABACI	1
	! OTHERS	OCIMUM BASILICUM	LIRIOMYZA SATIVAE	1
			LIRIOMYZA TRIFOLII	1
		ORIGANUM VULGARE	BEMISIA TABACI	1
PLANT PRODUCTS : ! OTHERS	OCIMUM BASILICUM	LIRIOMYZA TRIFOLII	1	
ISRAEL			<i>Sum:</i>	153

Country of Export	Commodity	Plant Species	Harmful Organism	No. of Interceptions
JORDAN	OTHER LIVING PLANTS : FRUIT & VEGETABLES	CORCHORUS OLITORIUS	BEMISIA TABACI	1
	OTHER LIVING PLANTS : LEAVES	CORCHORUS SP.	BEMISIA TABACI	1
JORDAN			<i>Sum:</i>	2

Country of Export	Commodity	Plant Species	Harmful Organism	No. of Interceptions
LEBANON	OTHER LIVING PLANTS : FRUIT & VEGETABLES	ALLIUM CEPA	THRIPIDAE	1
		CORCHORUS OLITORIUS	BEMISIA TABACI	2
		CORIANDRUM SATIVUM	THRIPIDAE	1
LEBANON			<i>Sum:</i>	4

Country of Export	Commodity	Plant Species	Harmful Organism	No. of Interceptions
TUNISIA	OTHER LIVING PLANTS : ! OTHERS	PHOENIX DACTYLIFERA	PYRALIDAE	1
	PRODUCTS : STORED PRODUCTS NOT CAPABLE OF GERMINATING	CERATONIA SILIQUA	COLEOPTERA	1
			EPHESTIA SP.	1
TUNISIA			<i>Sum:</i>	3

Country of Export	Commodity	Plant Species	Harmful Organism	No. of Interceptions
TURKEY	OTHER LIVING PLANTS : FRUIT & VEGETABLES	OCIMUM BASILICUM	LIRIOMYZA SP	2
	OTHER LIVING PLANTS : WARE POTATOES	SOLANUM TUBEROSUM	DITYLENCHUS DESTRUCTOR	1
TURKEY			<i>Sum:</i>	3

Annex 3b

List of EU's interceptions January 2013.

Interceptions of harmful organisms in commodities imported into the EU or Switzerland
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EUROPHYT- European Union
Notification System For Plant Health
Interceptions

Notified during the month of: JANUARY 2013

Country of Export	Commodity	Plant Species	Harmful Organism	No. of Interceptions
EGYPT	OTHER LIVING PLANTS : CUT FLOWERS AND BRANCHES WITH FOLIAGE	ASTER SP.	LIRIOMYZA TRIFOLII	1
	OTHER LIVING PLANTS : FRUIT & VEGETABLES	PISUM SATIVUM	HELICOVERPA ARMIGERA	1
EGYPT			<i>Sum:</i>	2

Country of Export	Commodity	Plant Species	Harmful Organism	No. of Interceptions
ISRAEL	INTENDED FOR PLANTING : CUTTINGS	CALIBRACHOA SP.	POTATO SPINDLE TUBER VIROID	1
		PETUNIA HYBRIDS	POTATO SPINDLE TUBER VIROID	1
		PETUNIA SP.	POTATO SPINDLE TUBER VIROID	1
	OTHER LIVING PLANTS : CUT FLOWERS AND BRANCHES WITH FOLIAGE	ASTER SP.	BEMISIA TABACI	1
		GYPSOPHILA SP.	LIRIOMYZA TRIFOLII	1
		LISIANTHUS SP.	BEMISIA TABACI	1
OTHER LIVING PLANTS : FRUIT & VEGETABLES	OCIMUM BASILICUM	BEMISIA TABACI	1	
<i>ISRAEL</i>			<i>Sum:</i>	7
LEBANON	OTHER LIVING PLANTS : FRUIT & VEGETABLES	ANNONA SP.	TEPHRITIDAE (NON-EUROPEAN)	1
<i>LEBANON</i>			<i>Sum:</i>	1
TURKEY	OTHER LIVING PLANTS : FRUIT & VEGETABLES	OCIMUM BASILICUM	BEMISIA SP.	1
			LIRIOMYZA SP	1
	OTHER LIVING PLANTS : WARE POTATOES	SOLANUM TUBEROSUM	CLAVIBACTER MICHIGANENSIS SUBSP. SEPEDONICUS	1
<i>TURKEY</i>			<i>Sum:</i>	3

Annex 4

List of EU's emergency measures on Q-pests March 2013.

Crop sector	Crops	Organism group	Species	Comments
1. Agriculture	Maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica virgifera</i>	
2. Agriculture	Potato	Insect	<i>Epitrix</i> spp.	
3. Agriculture	Potato, ornamentals	Virus etc.	Potato spindle tuber viroid	
4. Agriculture, *protected crops	Potato, tomato	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas solanacearum</i>	Import from Egypt
5. *Protected crops, agriculture	Flower ornamentals, vegetables	Insect	<i>Thrips palmi</i>	As regards Thailand
6. *Protected crops, field	Tomato	Virus etc.	Pepino mosaic virus	
7. Fruit	Sweet chestnut	Insect	<i>Dryocosmus kuriphilus</i>	
8. Fruit	Kiwi	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas syringae</i> pv. <i>actinidiae</i>	
9. Plants for planting, protected crops	Palms	Insect	<i>Rhynchophorus ferrugineus</i> , <i>R. palmarum</i> & <i>Paysandisia archon</i>	
10. Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i> & <i>A. chinensis</i>	
11. Plants for planting, forestry	Rhododendron, deciduous trees, etc	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i> & <i>P. kernoviae</i>	
12. Forestry	Pinus	Fungi	<i>Gibberella circinata</i>	
13. Forestry	Conifera	Nematode	<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>	

*Protected crops are glasshouse, screenhouse, plastic coverage etc.

Annex 5

Conclusions from the EUPHRESKO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of Balkan and Eastern Europe in Sofia 28th – 29th February 2012.

The following specific plant health pests were stressed as problems:

Maize fungi: *Stenocarpella macrocarpa*, (Geographic distribution EPPO/NEPPO: absent)

Maize fungi: *S. maydis*, Geographic distribution EPPO/NEPPO: Austria, Czech Republic and Italy)

Maize nematode: *Heterodera zea* (Geographic distribution EPPO/NEPPO: Egypt, Portugal)

Protected ornamentals and vegetables with special focus on thrips- and whitefly-transmitted viruses

Nepovirus in vine

Tuta absoluta in tomato production (Geographic distribution: present in EPPO/NEPPO region)